

**A STUDY OF JOB SATISFACTION AMONG HEALTHCARE EMPLOYEES IN
PUBLIC HOSPITAL AT RAIPUR AND ITS RELATIONSHIP WITH
PSYCHONEUROSIS**

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ABSTRACT

An effectively working health care system is not possible without a satisfied workforce with his/her job. Human factor is the primary resource of health care system, many dissatisfied health care work either quit their profession or leave their job for better opportunity. They are continuously facing a lot of stress other than the job; this is why the subject of dissatisfaction has gained attention in public health sector in Raipur. The study was done to assess the job satisfaction and psychoneurosis of health care worker and associated with different dimensional variable in public health hospital in Raipur and to assess the relationship between the two. The data was collected using Job Satisfaction Survey (JSS) questionnaire & General Health Questionnaire. The study was analyzed using SPSS-9. The levels were measured in Five-Point Likert's scale rating. The result of the study showed that most of the respondents are young and energetic and they are dissatisfied with their job, direct supervision, freedom to choose work method, salary, promotion, balance between family life and work life, reorganization and appreciation. Most of the health care employees are satisfied with their moral efficiency of work, team spirit and working environment, and with own moral. For Psychoneurosis, the age of the respondents and marital status is independent of psychoneurosis. Psychoneurosis are dependent on designation of the employees, working experience and presence of stress other than that related to job. Majority of the respondents shows high psychoneurosis and displayed both mental and physical symptoms. From the analysis the inference drawn is that respondents who are having high psychoneurosis are dissatisfied with their job.

KEYWORDS:- Job satisfaction, Psychoneurosis, Public Hospital, Healthcare Employees, Job Satisfaction Survey, Raipur

INTRODUCTION

Job Satisfaction

Job and Satisfaction are the two words that combined to form Job Satisfaction. To understand Job Satisfaction, it is essential to understand both the terms.

- a. Job: According to Oxford Dictionary, Job is defined as "Work for which you receive regular payment; a particular task or piece of work that you have to do"
- b. Satisfaction: According to Oxford Dictionary, Satisfaction is defined as "the good feeling that you have when you have achieved something or when something that you wanted to happen does happen; something that gives you this feeling; the act of fulfilling a need or desire; an acceptable way of dealing with a complaint, a debt, an injury, etc."
- c. Job Satisfaction: According to Oxford Dictionary, Job Satisfaction is defined as "the good feeling that you get when you have a job that you enjoy."

Job satisfaction can be defined as a fulfillment of an employee desires from their job. Job satisfaction can be fulfilled by having job stability, career growth, favorable working condition, job security, freedom, relationship with colleagues and superiors, promotion and their salary, autonomy, fairness in the workplace, appreciation of their merits. If these factors are achieved for an employee, he/she can be job satisfied.

An employee of an organization must always be satisfied because then only they can give their best for the given task. An employee needs a career growth and fairness at the work place. Job satisfaction can be seen with two perspectives: For Employees: According from employees' side it can be said as having a good salary, job stability, career growth, promotion and hikes contribute to job satisfaction.

For Employers: According from employers' side can be said as to get best out of the employees. If an employee is satisfied, they will give best out of them for the company or an organization. Employers have to safeguard his employees for giving them opportunities to all his employees for their career growth.

Job satisfaction has some positive effects:

1. Employees have good efficiency at working environment.
2. Employees are faithful to their responsibility.
3. Employee job satisfaction results for profits in companies.
4. Employees are satisfied then only employees will support to their fullest in an organization.

Job satisfaction comprises of some interpretation in areas namely: (1) job factors; (2) individual aspects; (3) relationship outside the job. The above factors are inter-related to each other in one or the other way. The approach which is selected for job satisfaction is viewed by the employees by its favorableness or un favorableness. The result obtained by the employees is calculated by their wants and expectations from their job. Moreover, many other factors must be included in the study of job satisfaction to completely understand the job satisfaction required by the employees. The factors may be: age, health, nature, enthusiasm and level of aspirations must be considered while understanding job satisfaction. Further, relationship with family, reputation, pleasure or hobbies, behavior in organizational- political and social, all contributes to job satisfaction.

Components of Job Satisfaction

- Personal or demographic factors such as Age, Sex, Dependents, Intelligence, Personality and Education.
- Job-inherent factors such as Type of work, Kind of Skills, Geography, Occupational status, Size of workplace
- Management controlled factors such as Working conditions, Security, Payment, Fringe benefits, Co-workers, Responsibilities and Supervision

PSYCHONEUROSIS

The psychoneurosis is minor mental disorder characterized by inner struggles and disturbed social relationship. Emotional stresses, conflicts and frustrations are the essential features of psychoneurosis and psychological techniques are effectively used to treat these features. Psychoneurosis are not produced by physical disorders and it is non-responsive to routine medical care.

OBJECTIVES

- To study the level of Job satisfaction among Healthcare Employees in Public Hospital at Raipur
- To study the factors associated with Job satisfaction among Healthcare Employees in Public Hospital at Raipur
- To study the Psychoneurosis among Healthcare Employees in Public Hospital at Raipur
- To find out the relationship between the Job Satisfaction and Psychoneurosis on Healthcare Employees in Public Hospital at Raipur

METHODOLOGY

The research design adopted was descriptive research. This research was undertaken to study the level of job satisfaction and the level of psychoneurosis disorders. A research design is purely a framework for a project that guides the collection and analysis of data. The main aim of such a design is to ensure that the required data are collected objectively, accurately and economically.

Sampling Design: A Cross sectional study using Non-Probabilistic Convenience sampling; and a stratified random sampling was conducted in public hospital in Raipur, Chhattisgarh which has more than 400 + beds. Data regarding number of staffs couldn't be found from the hospital but all those who were accessible from hospital including staff, part time employees, or ad hoc basis AV staff were involved in patient care were considered as study population. The sample involved health care worker of different strata including residential doctors, staff nurses, administration & management, paramedical staff & technicians, security. A well-structured questionnaire used for collecting the primary data from the employees which is used as the instrument for data.

A well-structured questionnaire used for collecting the primary data from the employees which is used as the instrument for data. Data collection was job satisfaction questionnaire encompassing the both the internal and external factors affecting job satisfaction of employees. Stress, payment, marital status, advancement opportunities and

working conditions, co-workers, responsibilities, and supervision. Through these factors in this job satisfaction (JSS), the different parameters under each area selected for the study will be asked to be rated by the respondents on a Five-Point Likert scale rating. The 12-item General Health Questionnaire (GHQ-12) was used for measuring mental disorders. The different parameters under each area selected for the study were asked to be rated by the respondents on a Four-Point Likert scale rating. Analysis carried out by assigning scores to these ratings given by the respondents to the different parameters under each area.

Data Collection and Analysis - A total of 300 questionnaire were distributed and collected over a period of two months. Out of 300, 232 responded (Response Rate of 78%) with the complete answers and all necessary precaution were taken to ensure that there are no missing values. The data was analyzed using (SPSS-9). Chi-Square Tests and correlation analysis was carried out.

Limitation - Limitation of this study are its use of self-reporting questionnaire, which rely on the honesty of those completing them and its cross-sectional design. It is not possible to assess completely the psychosomatic disorders within the given timeframe.

RESULTS

A study sample had shown (69.4%) Males and (30.6%) Females and 47.0% of them were in 20-25 Year Age Group. Were 42.7% married and 57.3% unmarried. 35 Resident Doctors, 70 Nurse Staff, 35 Admin & Management, 60 Paramed & Others, 32 Security. 141 worked in the hospital for less than 1 year, 83 for 1-5 year, 3 for 5-10 years, 5 had been more than 10 years, were 174 are having below 10,000 salaries. And 58 were having more than 10,000 salaries

Table 1. Socio-demographic characteristics of Health care Workers Working in Public Tertiary Care Hospital of Raipur, Chhattisgarh.

Socio Demographic Variable		Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	161	69.4
	Female	71	30.6
Age	20-25	109	47.0
	25-30	64	27.6
	30-35	37	15.9
	Above 35	22	9.5
Marital Status	Unmarried	133	57.3
	Married	99	42.7
Designation of the respondent	Res Doc	35	15.1
	Nursing	70	30.2
	Admin & Management	35	15.1
	Paramed & Others	60	25.9
	Security	32	13.8
Working experience	Less than 1 year	141	60.8
	1-5 year	83	35.8
	5-10 year	3	1.3
	More than 10 years	5	2.2
Salary of the respondent	Below 10,000	174	75.0
	More than 10,000	58	25.0

Chi- Square Test for each socio demographic characteristic:

1. Chi-Square Tests for Age of the respondents and job satisfaction

H0- Job Satisfaction is independent of Age group

H1- Job Satisfaction is dependent of Age group

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	8.398(a)	6	.210

Interpretation: Since the p value is more than 0.1 therefore, we accept the null hypothesis and reject the alternative hypothesis so, we conclude that the age group and job satisfaction are independent of each other i.e.; people of any age can have job satisfaction.

2. Chi-Square Tests for marital status of the respondents and job satisfaction

H0- Job Satisfaction is independent of marital status of the respondents

H1- Job Satisfaction is dependent of marital status of the respondents

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	4.663(a)	2	.097

Interpretation: Since the p value is less than 0.1 therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis so, we conclude that the marital status of the respondents and job satisfaction are dependent of each other i.e.; marital status of the respondent is the determining factor for job satisfaction.

3. Chi-Square Tests for working experience of the respondents and job satisfaction

H0- Job Satisfaction is independent of working experience of the respondents

H1- Job Satisfaction is dependent of working experience of the respondents

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	7.196(a)	6	.303

Interpretation: Since the p value is more than 0.1 therefore, we accept the null hypothesis and reject the alternative hypothesis so, we conclude that the working experience of the respondents and job satisfaction are independent of each other i.e.; working experience is not the determining factor for job satisfaction.

4. Chi-Square Tests for presence of stress other than job and job satisfaction

H0- Job Satisfaction is independent of presence of stress other than job

H1- Job Satisfaction is dependent of presence of stress other than job

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	2.770(a)	2	.250

Interpretation: Since the p value is more than 0.1 therefore, we accept the null hypothesis and reject the alternative hypothesis so, we conclude that the presence of stress other than job and job satisfaction are independent of each other i.e.; if the people are having stress factors (personal projects etc.) other than job than they are not dissatisfied with their jobs.

Chi- Square Test for each socio demographic characteristic:

1. Chi-Square Tests for Age of the respondents and psychoneurosis level

H0- Psychoneurosis is independent of Age group

H1- Psychoneurosis is dependent of Age group

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	5.872(a)	6	.438

Interpretation: Since the p value is more than 0.1 therefore, we accept the null hypothesis and reject the alternative hypothesis so, we conclude that the age group and psychoneurosis are independent of each other i.e.; people of any age can have psychoneurosis.

2. Chi-Square Tests for marital status of the respondents and psychoneurosis level

H0- Psychoneurosis is independent of marital status of the respondents

H1- Psychoneurosis is dependent of marital status of the respondents

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	.153(a)	2	.926

Interpretation: Since the p value is more than 0.1 therefore, we accept the null hypothesis and reject the alternative hypothesis so, we conclude that the marital status of the respondents and psychoneurosis are independent of each other i.e.; marital status of the respondent is not the determining factor for psychoneurosis.

3. Chi-Square Tests for working experience of the respondents and psychoneurosis level

H0- Psychoneurosis is independent of working experience of the respondents

H1- Psychoneurosis is dependent of working experience of the respondents

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	23.935(a)	6	.001

Interpretation: Since the p value is less than 0.1 therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis so, we conclude that the working experience of the respondents and psychoneurosis are dependent of each other i.e.; people who are having less working experience are showing high psychoneurosis.

4. Chi-Square Tests for presence of stress other than job and psychoneurosis level

H0- Psychoneurosis is independent of presence of stress other than job

H1- Psychoneurosis is dependent of presence of stress other than job

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	10.469(a)	2	.005

Interpretation: Since the p value is less than 0.1 therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis so, we conclude that the presence of stress other than job and psychoneurosis are dependent of each other i.e.; if the people are having stress factors (personal projects etc.) other than job than they are suffering from psychoneurosis.

Table 2. Frequency Table for job satisfaction and its various dimensions.

Job Satisfaction Variables	Frequency	Percentage	
	Highly Dissatisfied	34	14.7
Nature of work	Dissatisfied	147	63.4
	Neutral	34	14.7
	Satisfied	17	7.3
Direct Supervisor	Highly Dissatisfied	43	18.5
	Dissatisfied	131	56.5
	Neutral	32	13.8
	Satisfied	22	9.5
	Highly Satisfied	4	1.7

Values of views and participation	Highly Dissatisfied	9	3.9
	Dissatisfied	139	59.9
	Neutral	58	25.0
	Satisfied	22	9.5
	Highly Satisfied	4	1.7
Professionalism of hospital staffs	Highly Dissatisfied	15	6.5
	Dissatisfied	110	47.4
	Neutral	26	11.2
	Satisfied	75	32.3
	Highly Satisfied	6	2.6
With own morale	Highly Satisfied	21	9.1
	Satisfied	168	72.4
	Neutral	19	8.2
	Dissatisfied	22	9.5
	Highly Dissatisfied	2	.9
Recognition and appreciation	Highly Dissatisfied	20	8.6
	Dissatisfied	139	59.9
	Neutral	37	15.9
	Satisfied	32	13.8
	Highly Satisfied	4	1.7
Freedom to choose work method	Highly Dissatisfied	19	8.2
	Dissatisfied	136	58.6
	Neutral	49	21.1
	Satisfied	26	11.2
	Highly Satisfied	2	.9
Team spirit in working environment	Highly Satisfied	19	8.2
	Satisfied	155	66.8
	Neutral	40	17.2
	Dissatisfied	16	6.9
	Highly Dissatisfied	2	.9
Promotion program (GR1-12)	Highly Satisfied	1	.4
	Satisfied	43	18.5
	Neutral	41	17.7
	Dissatisfied	140	60.3
	Highly Dissatisfied	7	3.0
Balance between family life and work life	Highly Dissatisfied	14	6.0
	Dissatisfied	138	59.5
	Neutral	28	12.1
	Satisfied	45	19.4
	Highly Satisfied	7	3.0
Morale and efficiency of fellow workers	Highly Satisfied	15	6.5
	Satisfied	176	75.9
	Neutral	28	12.1
	Dissatisfied	12	5.2
	Highly Dissatisfied	1	.4

Interpretation: So, with the above frequency table, it can interpret that the majority (87.5%) of the respondents were found to be dissatisfied with their job and a few (9.1%) were found to be satisfied while 3.4% preferred to be remain neutral.

Table 3. Frequency Table for psychoneurosis and its various dimensions.

Psychoneurosis Variables		Frequency	Percentage
	much less than before	8	3.4
Ability to concentrate	same as before	145	62.5
	more than before	63	27.2
	much more than before	16	6.9
Sleep Cycle	much less than before	51	22.0
	same as before	114	49.1
	more than before	59	25.4
	much more than before	8	3.4
Playing a useful part in hospital working process	much less than before	15	6.5
	same as before	150	64.6
	more than before	58	25.0
	much more than before	9	3.9
Make decisions related to their department	much less than before	15	6.5
	same as before	150	64.7
	more than before	60	25.9
	much more than before	7	3.0
Constantly under strain	much less than before	32	13.8
	same as before	130	56.0
	more than before	57	24.6
	much more than before	13	5.6
Ability to cope up with difficulties	much less than before	103	44.4
	same as before	103	44.4
	more than before	21	9.1
	much more than before	5	2.2
Enjoy normal day to day activities	much less than before	22	9.5
	same as before	144	62.1
	more than before	56	24.1
	much more than before	10	4.3
Face up your problems	much less than before	28	12.1
	same as before	117	50.4
	more than before	80	34.5
	much more than before	7	3.0
Unhappy and depressed	much less than before	92	39.7
	same as before	120	51.7
	more than before	18	7.8
	much more than before	2	.9
Losing confidence in yourself	much less than before	123	53.0
	same as before	89	38.4
	more than before	16	6.9
	much more than before	4	1.7

Yourselves as a worthless person	much less than before	138	59.5
	same as before	85	36.6
	more than before	9	3.9
	much more than before	0	0.0
Reasonably happy, all things considered	much less than before	10	4.3
	same as before	67	28.9
	more than before	91	39.2
	much more than before	64	27.6
Headaches	much less than before	10	4.3
	same as before	67	28.9
	more than before	91	39.2
	much more than before	64	27.6
Fatigueness and exhausted	much less than before	22	9.5
	same as before	144	62.1
	more than before	56	24.1
	much more than before	10	4.3
Persistent Tension	much less than before	10	4.3
	same as before	67	28.9
	more than before	91	39.2
	much more than before	64	27.6
Aches and Pains	much less than before	51	22.0
	same as before	114	49.1
	more than before	59	25.4
	much more than before	8	3.4
Loss of voluntary control	much less than before	138	59.5
	same as before	85	36.6
	more than before	9	3.9
	much more than before	0	0.0
Gastrointestinal problems	much less than before	26	11.2
	same as before	83	35.8
	more than before	95	40.9
	much more than before	28	12.1

Interpretation: So, with the above frequency table, it can interpret that the majority (72.4%) of the respondents show high level of psychoneurosis, 7.8 % show moderate level of psychoneurosis while 19.8 % shows low psychoneurosis.

Table 5: Showing the level of Job Satisfaction of all the respondents

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Dissatisfied	203	87.5	87.5	87.5
	Neutral	8	3.4	3.4	90.9
	Satisfied	21	9.1	9.1	100.0
	Total	232	100.0	100.0	

Table 6: Showing the Status of Psychoneurosis of all the respondents

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Low	46	19.8	19.8	19.8
	Moderate	18	7.8	7.8	27.6
	High	168	72.4	72.4	100.0
	Total	232	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation: Majority (87.5%) of the respondents were found to be dissatisfied with their job, a few (9.1%) were found to be satisfied while 3.4% preferred to be neutral. According to the table given above, we can infer that majority (72.4%) of the respondents show high level of psychoneurosis, 7.8 % show moderate level of psychoneurosis while 19.8 % shows low psychoneurosis.

Table 7: Cross Tabulation between Job Satisfaction and Psychoneurosis

		RJBSTSF			Total
		Dissatisfied	Neutral	Satisfied	
Status of psychoneurosis	Low	38	2	6	46
	Moderate	15	1	2	18
	High	150	5	13	168
Total		203	8	21	232

Correlation between Job Satisfaction And Psychoneurosis to see whether any relationship exists between the two variables -

Table 8: Correlations between Job Satisfaction and Status of Psychoneurosis

		Status of psychoneurosis	RJBSTSF
Status of psychoneurosis	Pearson Correlation	1	-.084
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.201
	N	232	232
RJBSTSF	Pearson Correlation	-.084	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.201	.
	N	232	232

Interpretation: Since the value lies between +1 to -1 there is a relationship between the two variables. Since the value is negative it means there is a negative correlation which means that with the increase in the value of one variable the other decreases and vice-versa. An increase in psychoneurosis decreases job satisfaction. There is a low degree of correlation between the two variables.

Table 9: Correlations of Job satisfaction with other variables

		RJBSTSF	Age of the respondent	Marital Status of the respondent	Working experience	Presence of stress other than job	Presence of adolescent children
RJBSTSF	Pearson Correlation	1	.000	.025	.133	-.111	.050
Age of the respondent	Pearson Correlation	.000	1	.699	.310	-.126	-.254
Gender of the respondent	Pearson Correlation	.043	-.267	-.251	-.130	-.154	.039
Marital Status of the respondent	Pearson Correlation	.025	.699	1	.256	-.063	-.266
Designation of the respondent	Pearson Correlation	-.153	-.046	.112	-.254	.423	.042
Working experience	Pearson Correlation	.133	.310	.256	1	-.251	-.224
Presence of stress other than job	Pearson Correlation	-.111	-.126	-.063	-.251	1	.124
Presence of adolescent children	Pearson Correlation	.050	-.254	-.266	-.224	.124	1

INTERPRETATION: From the given table we can see that Job Satisfaction (dependent) is negatively correlated with the presence of stress other than job (independent variable). It implies that when the stress (independent variable) increases job satisfaction (dependent variable) decreases. Also Job Satisfaction is positively correlated with independent variables such as age, gender, marital status, presence of adolescent children/aged parents and working experience. It implies that these variables are less correlated i.e. increase in age, gender, marital status, presence of adolescent children/aged parents and working experience increases job satisfaction.

Table 10: Correlations of Psychoneurosis with other variables

INTERPRETATION: From the given table we can see that Psychoneurosis is negatively correlated with independent variables such as age of the respondents, marital status, working experience and presence of stress other than job. It implies that when these variables increase psychoneurosis decreases. Also, Psychoneurosis is positively correlated with the independent variable i.e; presence of adolescent children/aged parents. It implies that psychoneurosis increases with presence of adolescent children/aged parents in the family.

FINDINGS

Health system of Raipur is struggling with various blocks due to the economic, and awareness instability in region and one of those pivotal blocks is human resources for health. there is dissatisfaction in all walks of life which is observed in this developing country and healthcare resources are no exception. this is something which can be overlooked as it will in the long.

Only 9.1% of the study participants showed satisfaction with their job. Where 87.5% of the employees showed high dissatisfaction with their jobs. This has big suggestion for the public health system which is already facing shortage of financial resources and can't afford to lose the skilled workforce as dissatisfied workers leave their cities in search of better opportunities. The study revealed that the either doctors or nurses are not satisfied with their job, the improvement in the satisfaction of health service employees who are part and parcel of the health system and without whom the delivery of healthcare services to the needy can't be achieved.

Our study revealed that the participants had overall low satisfaction with various global dimension of the job with 59.9% were dissatisfied with the recognition and appreciation, 60.3% were dissatisfied with the promotion program (GR1-18) of the hospital, 59.5% were dissatisfied with their ability to maintain balance between family life and work life. All these results regarding recognition and appreciation, promotion, balance between family life and work life. Tally with the finding which were presented in the study reflecting job satisfaction in public health care workers in Raipur.

The result for direct supervision showed that most of the respondents were dissatisfied with the capabilities of their supervisor, the role he plays in mentoring them and showed overall liking for their supervisor with 9.5% of the opinion that they like their supervisor. This is particularly important in regards to healthcare industry like as worker deal with the patient not machine and learn to scale up the capabilities and if they believe that their supervisor lacks the ability to guide them and does not entrust them with task than add to skills and training should be provided to supervisor how

		status of psychoneurosis	Age of the respondent	Marital Status of the respondent	Working experience	Presence of stress other than job	Presence of adolescent children
status of psychoneurosis	Pearson Correlation	1	-.082	-.055	-.065	-.068	.086
Age of the respondent	Pearson Correlation	-.082	1	.699	.310	-.126	-.254
Gender of the respondent	Pearson Correlation	.089	-.267	-.251	-.130	-.154	.039
Marital Status of the respondent	Pearson Correlation	-.055	.699	1	.256	-.063	-.266
Designation of the respondent	Pearson Correlation	-.072	-.046	.112	-.254	.423	.042
Working experience	Pearson Correlation	-.065	.310	.256	1	-.251	-.224
Presence of stress other than job	Pearson Correlation	-.068	-.126	-.063	-.251	1	.124
Presence of adolescent children	Pearson Correlation	.086	-.254	-.266	-.224	.124	1

to deal with their subordinate. Most of the health worker enjoy offering the service to the mankind and think of the professionalism of hospital staff and take this as the opportunity to serve the humanity and feel pride to their job the satisfaction level were 32.5% and also good satisfaction percentage were observed in relationship with Morale and efficiency of fellow workers. Most of them enjoying the working with them and they count them a good team worker. The study showed that the most of our participants showed that marital status of were affected by the job satisfaction, they cannot balance between family life and worker life in both. And most of the healthcare worker faces family issues and stress. And disturbance in their daily life routine they can't control their work and family. The job satisfaction was 52.2 % increases the stress level in health worker other than job. And the working experience of the health worker increases the job satisfaction level, and Most of the respondents don't have adolescent children/aged parents in their family, also Job satisfaction are independent of presence of adolescent children/aged parents in the family, Most of the respondents have salary below 10,000/- and the salary is not enough to meet the cost of living, were most of the respondents are dissatisfied with their job i.e. 87.5%, while 3.4% were neutral in their job, 9.1 % were satisfied their job and other variable.

Low rates of job satisfaction create a difficult situation for health policy makers and planners, as low job satisfaction then translates into poor ability to render services to the community and resultantly services which are inefficient and ineffective. All the studies done in Raipur so far have nearly similar findings to our study which shows that no rigorous efforts have been taken by the public health sector to bring improvement in the job satisfaction of employees. The results cannot be ignored because if the same attitude continues in the future Raipur will keep on losing its skilled workforce to either foreign countries or people will be choosing other professions. Health sector workers undergo repetitive and difficult training drills in order to keep themselves abreast with latest advancements in the field of health. This involves a lot of money as well effort so it will be an irreversible loss if the skilled and trained health care workers leave their jobs because of dissatisfaction with the factors discussed above. In addition, all those who join an organization have the dream of growing with the organization where they render their services however if these dreams are not fulfilled its side effects can be seen as poor performance by the health worker and poor performing health system with unstable and always changing workforce.

From the study, it is found that the age of the respondents, marital status is independent of psychoneurosis. Psychoneurosis are dependent on designation of the employees i.e., resident doctors, nursing, administration, paramedical staff and security designations impact the level of psychoneurosis. As most of the respondents have work experience between 8 months to one year, it is found that the Psychoneurosis is dependent on working experience of the respondents. So, we can interpret that lesser the experience of the employee it is more likely to for them to develop the psychoneurosis or other related factors. Psychoneurosis is also found to be dependent on presence of stress other than that related to job (owning a car, house, personal problems etc.). Majority of the respondents shows high psychoneurosis i.e., 72.4% while 19.8 % shows low psychoneurosis and only 7.8 % shows moderate psychoneurosis. Psychoneurosis has been evaluated for both mental and physical symptoms. On mental symptoms, the employees feel that they have lost much sleep due to worry. When the employee is not able to complete the given work, it leads to stress/worry and ultimately lost sleep. Most of the employees feel that usually (constantly) they are under strains due to less leave allotment and heavy work load. Most of the employees feel that they can't cope with their difficulties. On physical symptoms, 95.7%, 90.5%, 95.7%, 88.8% and 77.9% of the respondents responded that they feel headache while doing work, fatigued and exhausted, feels tension, suffer from gastrointestinal problems and suffer from different aches and pains while working respectively. From the analysis the inference drawn is that respondents who are having high psychoneurosis are dissatisfied with their job; there is a negative correlation which indicates that if psychoneurosis increases job satisfaction decreases and the degree of correlation is less. Psychoneurosis decreases with increase in age of the respondents, marital status, working experience and presence of stress other than job. Also, Psychoneurosis increases with presence of adolescent children/aged parents in the family.

To overcome these, the employees should be allowed to take frequent breaks to avoid boredom, regular exercise like aerobics, calisthenics martial arts, weight training, walking, jogging, cycling, swimming or etc. should be done. Even sports like football, badminton, tennis, table tennis and squash can be healthy exercise. Different stretches like neck stretches, back stretches etc. should be taught to relax the body during working hours. Learn to say 'no'. Slow down and be honest about what you can comfortably do. Meditation should be encouraged to achieve relaxation by clearing the mind of stressful outside interferences. Meditation is becoming more widely accepted in the U.S. as a relaxation technique. Meditation reduces heart rate, blood pressure, adrenaline levels, and skin temperature. Hospital staff should be provided with recreation facilities inside the hospital, to relax during their working hours so. As nurses, front desk executives and paramedical staffs were the major ones having high psychoneurosis, they should be rotated in duties so that the change in workload can provide them with a chance to spend time for them and to keep them motivated at work.

CONCLUSION

From the analysis the inference drawn is that respondents who are having high psychoneurosis are dissatisfied with their job. There is a negative correlation which indicates that if psychoneurosis increases job satisfaction decreases and the degree of correlation is less. Presence of stress other than job (personal projects) decreases Job satisfaction. Also increase in age, gender, marital status, presence of adolescent children/aged parents and working experience increases job satisfaction. Psychoneurosis decreases with increase in age of the respondents, marital status, working experience and presence of stress other than job. Also, Psychoneurosis increases with presence of adolescent children/aged parents in the family. In Raipur health system is poor if we really need to improve the quality of health

care system, we need to pay special attention to improve the management system, quality and performance organization, And Proper performance appraisal techniques should be followed by the hospital, Periodic counselling of the employees should be done by the management, and Hospital staff should be provided with recreation facilities inside the hospital, to relax during their working hours.

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